

Protocol for 3D Models and Measurement

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Modified from Agisoft Metashape User Manual: Professional Edition, Version 1.8 and Measurement Protocol by Evelyn Sanchez

Making The Model

Importing Photos to Agisoft44

1. Open Agisoft Metashape.
2. Click on the **Workflow** menu and select **Add Photos**.

3. Browse to the location where the photostopped photos are stored and select them all. Click **Open** (bottom right) to import the photographs into Metashape. The photos should appear next to the Workspace.

Masking (Skip)

1. Right click on one of the photos in the workspace and hover over **Masks**. Select **Generate Masks...**

2. For **Method**, select **From Background Image**. For **Operation**, select **Replacement**. For **Filename Template**, put the name of the background image file. For now, **Apply to Selected images** to test the mask. Play around with the tolerance level until the mask looks right (a higher tolerance will include less of the object, whereas a lower tolerance will include more of the object).

3. When you are happy with the mask, repeat steps 1-2 but **Apply to All images**. You can check the masks by toggling **Show Masks** within the photos tab. Masks should generally follow the shape of the bee and not leave important features out. Models with poor masks

still can generate cleanly – before masking manually, run the model first to see how it looks.

Aligning Photos, Building Mesh/Model, Building Texture, and Smoothing

1. Under [Workflow](#), click [Align Photos](#).
2. Make sure the presets are as follows:

3. Press [OK](#). Agisoft will ask you to name the file. Name it `catalog#_full_model.psx`, and make sure it goes in the correct folder. Agisoft should spend 5-10 minutes aligning after you click [Save](#).
 - a. Ex: UCSB-IZC00036327_full_model.psx

4. After aligning, you should see the tie points under the Model tab.

5. Under [Workflow](#), click [Build Model](#). Set the presets as such:

- a. Note: Some versions of Agisoft say [Build Mesh](#), rather than [Build Model](#).

6. Press **OK**. Agisoft should spend 15-20 minutes building the model.

7. Once you have your model, click **Build Texture...** under **Workflow**. Make sure it has the below settings. It should take less than 5 minutes.

- To smooth the model, go to **Tools > Model > Smooth Model**. Use the below settings.

- Note: When you smooth the model, Agisoft may automatically duplicate the model (under Chunk 1, you will see two models labeled “3D Model”). Rename the top model “Full Model” and the bottom model “FB,” like below.

Saving The Model

- Congrats, you’ve made a 3D model! Now we need to save it.
 - If the model file is already named, just go to **File > Save**.
 - If the model file is unnamed, go to **File > Save As....** Name the model catalog#_model.psx.
- Make sure the file is in the correct folder. It should be in the same folder as the folder with the JPEGs.
- Now, save the metadata of the file. Go to **File > Export > Generate Report**. Name the metadata file catalog#_full_model_metadata.pdf.

Model Iterations

Making The Measurement Model

1. Using the “full model,” we will now make a “measurement model,” which we can use to measure the bee’s volume and surface area.
2. We start with removing the pin and the stage (if visible). Select the [Free-Form Selection](#) tool in the top left corner.

3. Carefully select the part that needs to be deleted. Play around with different angles until you have selected only the parts you need to delete. Try to preserve any parts of the bee’s body as much as you can. If needed, select small portions at a time and incrementally delete chunks until what you need is gone.

- a. The best method for preserving the bee body is to find angles where the parts you want to cut are not overlapping with other parts of the bee. As seen above, the pin (which is being cut) is not overlapping with any of the bee’s body or wings.
 - b. Tip: Quickly toggle between the [Selection](#) tool and the [Navigation](#) tool using the spacebar.
 - c. Tip: Use [Edit > Grow Selection/Shrink Selection](#) to incrementally change the selection as needed before deleting.
4. Once the part is selected, go to [Edit > Delete Selection](#).
 5. Repeat steps 3 and 4 until the entirety of the pin and stage are gone.
 6. Now, begin to cut excess hair. This is rather discretionary, but make the best judgement call. Try to maintain the shape and size of the bee. You can look at the specimen itself to determine what is hair on the model and what isn’t.

- a. Before and after cutting excess hair. Somewhat of an extreme example.

- b. A more common example.

7. Once all the excess hair is cut, go to [Tools](#) > [Model](#) > [Close Holes...](#). This step is essential to obtaining morphometrics! The holes should be 100% closed (when prompted).
8. Now you can save the new file. Go to [File](#) > [Save As...](#), and save it as catalog#_measurement_model.psx.

Model Iterations

1. There are several model iterations needed to measure the body segments in different ways. To duplicate the model, go to [Workspace](#) > [Chunk 1](#) > [FB](#) (right click) >

Duplicate.

- a. Note: Make sure you do not duplicate the entire chunk. Instead, only duplicate the model within the chunk.
2. Overall, there will be twelve iterations of the model, as listed below. The code is used for inputting the data in the measurement spreadsheet. Duplicate the model until there are 12 copies (13 total models including the original).

Code	Meaning	Example
FB	Full body, no tongue, no antenna	

H	Head, no tongue, no antenna	
A	Abdomen	
NW	Full body, no wings, no tongue, no antenna, legs attached	

S	Full body, no tongue, no wings, no antenna, no legs	
ST/T	Thorax, no wings or legs	

3. Rename each iteration with its code for organization.

4. For each iteration, make the needed adjustments. Make sure to close holes at the end of every new model. Once you close holes, check to make sure that the model still roughly follows the shape of the bee; if not, you can do some more cutting. We are looking to preserve the shape and size of the bee as much as possible.

- a. For efficiency (i.e., spending as little time cutting as possible), here is the recommended model flow:

5. Make sure to save frequently so as to not unintentionally lose progress.
6. Once all iterations have been created, we are ready to measure!

Measuring The Model

Making The Scale Bar

1. Open the scale bar image with Photoshop.

2. Select the Line Tool:

3. Using the Line Tool, draw a line of length 10mm or 20 mm (depending on your magnification and how much of the scale bar fits in the frame of the photo).

4. Change the size of the line to 20px and the tilt of the line to 0° (under the Appearance box). The line color should contrast the background color (e.g., a black background needs a white scale bar).

5. Once your line is drawn, right click the Background layer and press [Delete Layer](#).

6. Select the Horizontal Type tool. Type either “10 mm” or “20 mm,” depending on the length of your line. Set the font to 100 pt and center the text over the line.

7. With the background still invisible, right click on the Line or Text layer and select [Merge Visible](#).

8. Right click the background image and [Delete Layer](#).
9. Once this is done, the file is ready to be Saved. Go to [File > Save As...](#) > and save the scale bar as a type Photoshop (*.PSD) file. Save the scale bar to the larger JPEG folder, not the smaller.
10. Once you have saved the scale bar to your folder, rename the file. It should have the format: catalog#_scalebar.psd
 - a. Example: UCSB-IZC00038960_scalebar.psd

Creating Scale Bars for [Metashape](#)

1. Select an image with a head-on point-of-view of the bee. Open it in Photoshop.
2. Drag the scale bar from earlier onto the image in Photoshop.
3. Save the image by clicking [Save As...](#). Keep the same file name and add _scalebar.jpeg.
4. Open [ImageJ](#). Select [File > Open > Select Local File](#), and open the image with the scale bar.
5. Zoom in. Use the line tool to draw across the length of the scale bar in the image.

6. Click **Analyze > Set Scale...** Enter the known length from the scale bar under Known Distance. Press **OK**.

Prepping The Scale Bars in Agisoft

1. In ImageJ, draw a straight line between two recognizable points on the bee.
 - a. **Good points** include the base of the antennae, the corners of the compound eyes, and from the ocellus to the mouth.
 - b. Typically, Agisoft responds better to smaller scale bars. Make the points on places closer together for more accuracy and easier measuring.

2. Click [Analyze](#) > [Measure](#). Note the length determined on the right side of the pop-up.

3. In Agisoft, navigate to the head-on photo under the Photos tab. Place markers on the exact same points as the ends of the line in Image J. To do so, right click on the point you

need on the photo of the bee (e.g., top left corner of marker settings box below).

4. Select the two points in the Markers tab in Agisoft. Right click and [Create Scale Bar](#).

5. Set the Distance to the known length determined in Image J. Set the Accuracy to 1.000000.
6. A blue, green, or gray flag should appear over each photo.
 - a. A blue flag indicates that the software detects a marker but needs manual verification that the marker is in the right spot.
 - b. A green flag means the marker is verified.
 - c. A gray flag means that the software does not detect the marker. No action required for white flags.
7. If an image has a blue flag, double click it. Verify the marker is in the right location. If it is, verify by clicking on the marker. If it is not in the right location, move it and verify (if possible). If the marker cannot be verified, right click it and [Remove Projection](#).
 - a. Note: Some markers will be “stubborn,” meaning Agisoft will continually try detecting a point where you cannot verify. If needed, right click the marker and select [Block Marker](#).

- b. To minimize error, try to shorten the distance of the green line that appears next to green flags. The line indicates the direction and relative magnitude of distance away from where Agisoft thinks the marker is. The program can be wrong, so always use best judgement of the point first (Agisoft may re`te and align with where the point actually is).
8. The scale bar is ready when there are no blue flags remaining.
9. Repeat steps 1-8 two more times until you have three different verified scale bars.

Data Collection

1. Once you have all the scale bars confirmed, you can begin measuring the bee. Beginning with the FB model, select one scale bar on the left hand side of Agisoft and click [Update Transform](#) in the Reference panel.

2. Go to [Tools](#) > [Model](#) > [Measure Area and Volume](#).
 - a. Tip: If the volume is zero but the surface area is nonzero, make sure you [Close Holes](#) on the model.
3. Enter the volume and surface area measurements in to the [3D models: volume & area measurements](#) spreadsheet under the first measurement column.
4. Repeat steps 1-3 with the remaining scale bars and the subsequent measurement columns.
 - a. Note: You can tell that you have done your scale bars well if all of your measurements are relatively close to one another. You can also check the error between the scale bars on Agisoft. If a measurement from a scale bar looks like it has high deviation from the other two scale bars, consider redoing that scale bar with two different points on the bee. The goal is for all three measurements to be within a normal margin of error.
5. Now, select all three scale bars and [Update Transform](#). Measure the surface area and volume. Add this data to the Agisoft Average columns.
6. In the spreadsheet, compute the average surface area and volume using the values obtained by the three different scale bars. Add this value to the Arithmetic Average columns.
 - a. In Google Sheets, you can select the cell where you want the Arithmetic Average and type in `=average(Value_1, Value_2, Value_3)` to compute the average. The respective values are those computed from each scale bar. You can input the

values manually or just click each cell to enter into the equation and a comma in between them.

7. Repeat steps 1-6 for every iteration of the model.
8. With all measurements completed, the process is finished!

Batch Modeling (Alternative)

Batch modeling video

*test editing metadata